

Students' Attitudes Towards Learning English Language Vocabulary: Pillars of A Development Roadmap

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Abstract

This study investigated the attitudes of non-medical college students at DMC College Foundation, Inc. toward learning English vocabulary and examined how these attitudes relate to their academic performance in the Purposive Communication course. A quantitative-descriptive approach was employed, with data gathered through structured questionnaires designed to assess the behavioral, cognitive, and emotional components of student attitudes. The findings revealed that students generally held favorable emotional and cognitive attitudes toward vocabulary learning, while their behavioral engagement appeared more reserved or neutral. In general, attitudes toward vocabulary learning were positive. In terms of academic performance, students demonstrated commendable achievement in the course. Statistical analysis found no significant relationship between their attitudes and academic performance. However, emotional attitudes varied notably when compared across gender and academic programs, suggesting that emotional engagement in language learning is influenced by demographic factors. Based on these results, the study recommends the use of emotionally engaging and contextually relevant strategies to support vocabulary acquisition, particularly for students enrolled in technical courses. Additionally, promoting more active behavioral participation is advised to foster alignment between student attitudes and academic outcomes.

Keywords: Academic Performance, DMC College Foundation, Emotional Engagement, English Vocabulary, Student Attitude

Introduction

Language is the cornerstone of human interaction, serving as a vehicle for communication, cultural expression, and intellectual development. Among the languages spoken across the globe, English stands out as the most widely used second language, serving as the global lingua franca in various domains such as international business, science, technology, diplomacy, and education. In the Philippines, English holds a unique status as one of the official languages and is extensively used as a medium of instruction, especially in higher education. As such, proficiency in the English language is not only essential for academic success but also for professional advancement in the increasingly interconnected world.

Language is an essential instrument for communication. It's not only enabling interpersonal connections and cultural ties but also functions as a means of reasoning and sharing ideas. A language showcases the uniqueness of cultures within a country, area, or community while emphasizing their differences. The way individuals view the world is influenced by their language. Additionally, it plays a significant role in shaping the culture of a society (Tenedero and Trinidad, 2023).

According to Amelia (2018), English is a necessary language, especially in the digital age. For students who are not specialized in English vocabulary, understanding effective vocabulary learning strategies becomes crucial, helps increase their chances of being hired, and improves coherence in written and spoken communication. However, the time spent on vocabulary in class is often quite little. In this study, attitude is considered as an essential factor in determining academic performance in learning English vocabulary. Vocabulary learning is critical to learning a language. Teachers must be knowledgeable in choosing which strategies would greatly improve students' reading performance in class. Vocabulary learning is one of the major challenges faced by language learners, and it is impracticable for a learner to communicate without the necessary vocabulary items. However, a learner cannot learn all vocabulary in language classes, so he/she must seek other useful ways to help her acquire language vocabulary in the best way (Kebede, 2022). Moreover, it is impossible for a learner to communicate without the required vocabulary. Indeed, a number of scholars in the field of vocabulary believe that communication can occur without syntax and grammar, but not vocabulary. As such, it cannot be denied that if learners have no vocabulary, they cannot express their ideas, thinking or feelings as well as are unable to understand the meaning of written and spoken texts. Thus, vocabulary learning is a prominent domain to approach a satisfactory language proficiency level.

Amelia (2018) elaborated that student's attitudes about learning English are a complex topic that calls for an all-encompassing approach. To create efficient language teaching and learning strategies, it is essential to comprehend the interaction of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, the effects of the learning environment and teaching methodology, the perception of difficulty, and the influence of cultural variables.

The connection between attitudes and language ability has been extensively studied. Higher levels of linguistic proficiency have been linked to positive attitudes, according to studies. The relationship is intricate and not always clear-cut, though. While success can be influenced by positive attitudes, success can also be influenced by proficiency; students who succeed may grow to have more positive views toward the language (Yuksel et al, 2024).

In the Philippine higher education context, the Purposive Communication course plays a vital role in strengthening students' English language skills. As part of the general education curriculum, this course is designed to develop students' communicative competence across various modes and platforms—oral, written, visual, and digital. It emphasizes the effective use of English in academic, professional, and social settings, encouraging students to become thoughtful and strategic communicators. Within this course, vocabulary enrichment is not merely about memorization but is interwoven into tasks such as academic writing, public speaking, report-making, and the analysis of texts and media. Hence, the students' attitude toward learning vocabulary has a significant impact on how they engage with the course and on the development of their overall communication proficiency.

Purposive Communication is a general education course that focuses on the effective use of communication in various contexts academic, professional, and intercultural—through written, oral, visual, and digital forms. It aims to develop students' skills in purposeful, audience-sensitive, and context-appropriate communication to prepare them for global and multicultural settings (Dayag et al, 2016).

Attitudes toward vocabulary can influence how students participate in class discussions, complete writing assignments, and interact with academic texts. Furthermore, students' attitudes are shaped by a multitude of factors, including previous learning experiences, teaching strategies, classroom environment, perceived usefulness of the language, peer influence, and their confidence in their own language abilities.

Several studies have been made on English language learning and acquisition, most of these studies used various variables such as secondary school learners and non-native English speakers. For the current study, the researchers will investigate the students' attitude towards learning English language vocabulary and will utilize the college students of DMC College Foundation, Inc. where the researchers are currently enrolled.

As English majors, the researchers understand how important vocabulary is to communication and linguistic competency. Nevertheless, despite the wealth of studies on language learning and acquisition, little attention is paid to the precise ways in which students' attitudes affect their vocabulary acquisition, especially among college students in the Philippine educational system. Few studies have looked at the specific behavioral, cognitive, and emotional markers that influence students' vocabulary acquisition, despite the fact that many have investigated overall attitudes about learning English.

Furthermore, language teaching has changed due to the quick development of digital learning resources and technology; nevertheless, little is known about how students' attitudes toward vocabulary acquisition are affected by these contemporary learning environments. By investigating how different factors impact vocabulary development and offering insights that could improve teaching methods and curriculum design for English language education thus, the researchers hope to close this gap.

This study aimed to examine students' perspectives and experiences in learning English vocabulary, which may contribute to a better understanding of effective learning strategies. More specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1 gender;
 - 1.2 age; and
 - 1.3 program?
2. What is the level of students' attitude in learning English language in terms of:
 - a. behavioral indicators;
 - b. cognitive indicators; and
 - c. emotional indicators?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondents in their Purposive Communication course during the first semester, academic year 2024-2025?
4. Is there a significant difference between the students' attitude towards learning English language vocabulary when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' attitude towards learning English language vocabulary and their academic performance?

Literature Review

Students Attitude in Learning English Vocabulary

According to Ghanizadeh & Jahedizadeh (2020), the study of students' attitudes toward learning English vocabulary has gained prominence due to the increasing role of English as a global language. Attitude is shaped by various factors, including behavioral, cognitive, and emotional indicators, which influence motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes. Learning English vocabulary during the pandemic era posed challenges for educators. These challenges stemmed from the effectiveness of online learning platforms and the learning atmosphere fostered through interactions between lecturers and students. Student engagement, as a key factor in learning success, played a crucial role in overcoming these challenges. Additionally, significant factor affecting students' attitudes is the role of error treatment in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning. Findings indicate that students' attitudes toward vocabulary learning

are influenced by their perception of errors, correction methods, and motivational factors. Notably, students with positive cognitive engagement demonstrate better vocabulary retention

Moreover, Anwar & Abdullah (2021) stated that individuals' attitudes towards the learning English language vary on the learning context that affects their success in learning language in general. Many lecturers have different strategies used in their class in order to recognize the target students' attitudes, these attitudes are geared towards a specific language that could either produce positive or negative results (Gardi et al, 2020). Attitudes towards learning the English language have an impact on behaviors such as choosing and reading books, listening to English radio, watching English channels etc. Particularly in academics, in case a student has a positive attitude towards learning English language, they will be able to attain many things in that particular area (Prabhu et al., 2020).

According to Garcia (2019) attitude is the values of every person in the whole world, their individual personality and how they act every day in our daily life. The students who have a good attitude towards studies have a tendency to be successful someday. Student`s attitude has a great impact on their academic performances. Many students are experiencing failing grades and low academic performance because of not showing attention or interest toward their studies, absenteeism, cutting classes and participating well in class, especially boys. The students who try to make progress in their studies with a positive attitude are always successful, while those who are negative in their behavior are more concerned about the negative outcomes which lead to their failures.

Monteroso and Baes (2024) stated that to be successful in language learning and teaching, it is important to understand the learners' attitudes toward learning the English language. Thus, English is used as a second language in the country, attitudes of learners toward learning English play an important role in the success of learning the language.

Behavioral Indicators

The behavioral component of attitude focuses on how a person acts or responds to a specific circumstance. Kara (2009) holds that having happy views causes one to display favorable behaviors toward study programs, with participants taking in enrolling in classes and making an effort to learn more. These kinds of learners are also seen to have a greater desire to learn and solve challenges and abilities to interact emotionally as well as for everyday living (Khan et al, 2020).

Attitude is defined as individuals' feelings about conducting a particular behavior. It was theorized and empirically proved to have a significant and positive effect on behavioral intention in general domains and technology-based learning. Subjective norm is viewed as an individual's perceptions of performing a specific behavior influenced by important persons (Saab et al., 2022).

According to Ahmed et al., (2021), many students begin learning English from primary school; some others from kindergarten or even from day care; however, the issue is that many of them are not able to accomplish the desired level of English proficiency, the main reason is de-motivation of students in all levels. Student`s attitude is an essential portion of learning; consequently, attitude is considered a vital factor of language learning. Attitude towards learning English is supposed to affect attitude for instance choosing and reading the right material, communicating with a native English speaker and so on.

According to Gettie (2020), there are three types of speakers using English: those who speak it as a first language (around 375 million speakers), those who speak it as a second or additional language (again some 375 million speakers), and those who learn it as a foreign language (about 750 million learners).

According to some researchers, the main reason for student failure in secondary school is the inability to study through the medium of English and determining it as a foreign language which restricts students' opportunities to practice outside the classroom, which is an informal way of learning (Gettie, 2020). There is some research findings conducted locally regarding the attitude of students towards learning English as a foreign language. For instance, Gettie (2020) conducted on this topic and both of them show that students have negative attitudes towards their English learning. However, the study conducted by (Augier et al., 2020) indicated that social influence was not significantly related to behavioral intention in the context of social learning system use. Moreover, some researchers stated that the influence of social influence on technology adoption was complex and varied across contexts (Saab et al., 2022).

According to (Khan et al., 2020) people who have favorable attitudes toward their studies show positive behaviors toward them, immersing themselves in the material and making an effort to learn more. These children are also seen to be more motivated to solve issues, learn practical knowledge and skills, and express their emotions, how someone acts or responds to a specific circumstance is the focus of the behavioral component of attitude. This strong relationship between attitude and behavior is predicated on the idea that the two are constant and that one's actions should reflect their attitude. A person's behavior can be accurately predicted by their attitude, and the more strongly they hold an attitude, the more that attitude will influence their actions. Khan et al., (2020) shows an emphasis on the concept of a collective mind. As language is not only a social product of the community but also a tool for fostering a specific social thought in the individual, it supports the idea that personality development is dependent on cultural and community influences, particularly through language.

Since self-regulated learning is a behavioral manifestation of metacognitively guided motivation, as stated by Winne and Baker (2013), each trace documents a motivated decision regarding learning. By analyzing trace data, one can gain a deeper understanding of and uncover significant behavioral trends regarding time management, effort expenditure, and advancement rate.

Cognitive Indicators

Cognitive engagement is defined as learners' psychological processes of understanding complex ideas, deploying self-regulation, and mastering difficult skills (Lan et al., 2024). The cognitive domain is the area that incorporates mental exercises including the cycle of acknowledgment and/or disclosure that centers on the conception, the preservation, the remembrance, and the presentation of facts Wang (2021). Similarly, it incorporates relationships between components, idea arrangement, issue disclosure, and problem-solving abilities, which thus structure novel considerations.

Additionally, Wang (2021) expounded that mental exercises identified with the cognitive domain include thinking, reasoning, admiring, and envisaging. The affective domain is the area identified with mentalities and qualities which highlight the outlook and emotional state of students toward learners and/or teachers. The mentality is one of the terms in the field of psychology which deals with insight and practice that can similarly be deciphered as a construct to permit seeing an activity. The idea of mentality itself can be observed from different related components such as mentality with character, thought processes, confidence level, and so on.

In order to better understand how students learn to write and how to help close the achievement gap in the writing skills of the expanding Hispanic English learning population, a recent study from the University of Kansas is one of the first of its kind to look at cognitive functions and their role in teaching English learners to write in their second language (Krings, 2023).

Moreover, Krings (2023) discussed that students' performance in writing and all other cognitive skills improved. However, working memory was the only factor that consistently predicted higher writing scores. According to Orosco (2010), this highlights the value of working memory, particularly the ability to quickly recall words and concepts while writing. Furthermore, it implies that if native language instruction is not offered in schools, students may not be enhancing their oral language development and phonological awareness skills, despite the fact that they are naturally fluent in their mother tongue.

The cognitive processes of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners have been the subject of research in listening evaluation. When it comes to multiple choice questions (MCQs), the majority of studies use correct answers as data, but they undervalue the rich information of incorrect answers or options. However, the MCQ distractions are frequently purposefully created to highlight the difficulties or obstacles faced by students (Meng et al., 2023).

The need to determine the traits of successful learners gave rise to the literature on learning strategies in foreign language acquisition. Research on "good language learners" has found tactics that students have reported adopting or seen in language learning contexts that appear to aid in learning. These initiatives showed that students use categorized and characterized learning processes when learning a foreign language. O'Malley and Chamot viewed learning processes as cognitive skills, heavily influenced by the results of cognitive psychology. Three categories have been established for

learning strategies based on the type or level of processing that is engaged. These include cognitive, social/affective, and meta-cognitive methods. Higher order executive skills known as meta-cognitive methods can include organizing, observing, or assessing the effectiveness of a learning exercise. Incoming information is directly manipulated by cognitive techniques to improve learning. According to Lou and Xu (2016), social/affective tactics are a broad category that includes ideational control over affect or engagement with another person.

Emotional Indicators

Positive emotions are crucial for successful language learning because they increase motivation, engagement, and overall academic performance. On the other hand, not much research has been done on how language instructors feel and communicate happy feelings during teaching Lung (2024).

Different experts have defined attitude in different ways. According to Li & Wei (2022), for instance, a student's behavior reflects their attitudes toward the language and the language class. Therefore, a person with a good attitude will have strong views that the conduct will lead to positively valued results. On the other hand, a person with a negative attitude will have strong views that the conduct would lead to results that are not appreciated. Tarnopolsky et al., (2020) describe attitude as a psychological inclination to have a favorable or unfavorable opinion on a specific behavior or item. Students' sentiments, convictions, and behavioral patterns in relation to their language learning endeavors are referred to as their language learning attitude. Therefore, educators and teachers should take attitude and behavior into account when developing strategies for English language training and instruction. Determining the probability of an educational program's success requires an understanding of attitudes. Having a positive outlook makes learning much easier. A student will not succeed if they lack motivation or have a pessimistic outlook.

Every student has an attitude, whether it be positive or bad, according to the different definitions of attitude given above. It seems that this mindset affects whether pupils succeed or fail in their language learning endeavors. Students tend to undervalue the lessons when they approach learning with a bad mindset. On the other hand, pupils who approach their studies with excitement and a positive attitude pay great attention to the courses (Tarnopolsky et al., 2020).

Vocabulary learning in a second and/or foreign languages is needed to make effective communication and it is impossible to use a language effectively without an adequate vocabulary (Çinar & Asım, 2019) behaviors, inner mood and therefore learning environmental components in which the student grows up. Both negative and positive attitudes have a strong impact on the success of language learning. Experts have provided various definitions of attitude. For example, Li & Wei (2022) stated that the student behaves in accordance with his or her attitudinal evaluations of the language and language class. Thus, a person who holds strong beliefs that positively valued outcomes will result from performing the behavior will have a positive attitude. Conversely, a person who holds strong beliefs that negatively valued outcomes will result from the behavior will have a negative attitude.

Moreover, Botes et al., (2020) also point out that language attitude is linked to motivation (instrumental or integrative) and emotion (positive or negative), both of which have been evidenced as significant factors of language achievement. This means that students will naturally react with their emotion, and motivation when they are placed in a learning situation. The definition of attitude in relation to language learning is extensively covered in the published literature.

According to Boland et al (2024) there are three factors: motivation, and anxiety—can influence a student's success in learning a second language. Students' attitudes are a major role in determining their success in language acquisition. Undoubtedly, for learning to occur effectively, teachers need their students to have a good mindset. Getie & Popescu (2020) claimed that attitude affects students' behavior, mood, and, consequently, learning, and they endorse this. Therefore, it is evident that language acquisition and the contextual factors a pupil is exposed to during their upbringing interact. Both positive and negative attitudes significantly impact the success of language learning.

Methodology

This study is quantitative-correlational in nature. According to Unimrkt Research (2023), using quantitative research methods, which concentrate on objective measurement and statistical analysis of data to provide a concise and easily

understood summary of the research topic, numerical data is systematically collected and analyzed to describe or summarize a population or phenomenon.

The study was conducted at DMC College Foundation Inc., Fr. Patangan Road, Sta Filomena, Dipolog City, Zamboanga Del Norte, Philippines. The research setting is located in a convenient area that provides a suitable environment for conducting research, where researchers can easily access it in case of sudden changes.

Additionally, DMC has a strong foundation in healthcare education; DMC College Foundation Inc. has steadily expanded its academic offerings to include a diverse range of non-medical programs that cater to the evolving demands of various industries. These include programs in Information Technology, Business Administration, Hospitality Management, and Education.

DMC College Foundation is now a solid, successful landmark of the province of Zamboanga del Norte. Superior in work ethic and skills, the thousands of graduates DMC College Foundation has produced over the years made remarkable contributions to the health care workforce and to other fields in the locality, in other regions, and even in other parts of the globe. DMC College Foundation sees an opportunity to grow amidst challenges, the very attitude it inculcates among its students.

The respondents of the study are first-year non-medical college students who are currently enrolled in the first semester of the 2024-2025 school year from the College of Computer Studies and the School of Teacher Education, as these are the only two departments that completed the Purposive Communication course in that semester. The researchers want to narrow the population.

The students coming from DMC College Foundation possess strong social skills. Beyond academics, they take responsibility for their learning. They show respect for their teachers and other members of the school community. They show a genuine curiosity about the subject matter and a willingness to learn beyond the curriculum. The researchers will utilize purposive sampling for this study. Purposive sampling is used when a study focuses in depth on relatively small samples or a particular subset of the population that shares certain characteristics. The total population for this study is 46.

The total population for this study is 46 because it represents the specific group of first-year non-medical college students from the College of Computer Studies and the School of Teacher Education at DMC College Foundation, Inc. who are officially enrolled in the second semester of the academic year 2024–2025. The term non-medical program refers to academic tracks that do not focus on health sciences or medical-related fields. In this study, it specifically includes programs such as the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) and the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED), which emphasize technical and pedagogical disciplines rather than clinical or biomedical training. Focusing on non-medical students allows the study to explore English vocabulary learning attitudes in contexts where English is applied differently than in health-related programs, such as in technology and education.

Since purposive sampling is used, the researchers intentionally selected this subset of students based on their relevance to the study's objectives. The number 46 is determined by the actual number of students meeting the inclusion criteria which are the regular non-medical college students, ensuring that the sample is appropriate for analyzing students' attitudes toward learning English vocabulary.

Research Instrument

This study utilized an adapted questionnaire from the study of Tenedero, C. et. al (2023) entitled Investigating Students Attitude in Learning English Language Vocabulary: The case of Engineering Students in Technological University of the Philippines.

The instrument covers two parts (a) respondents' demographic and (b) attitude indicators in learning English. The first part includes age, gender and program of the respondents. The second part of the instrument includes a five-point Likert

scale relating to the attitudes of the respondents in learning English in terms of their behavioral, cognitive and emotional indicators. Each indicator has ten statements.

Table 1. Scoring Procedure

Score	Scale Range	DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENT INTERPRETATION	LEVEL OF
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative Attitude
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Negative Attitude
3	2.61-3.40	Neither/ Nor Agree	Neutral or Uncertain Attitude
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	Positive Attitude
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive Attitude

Table 2. Grading Point System

GRADE	QUALITY MARKS	QUALITY POINTS
1.0	Excellent	95 and above
1.25	Superior	93 to 94
1.5	Very Good	90 to 92
1.75	Good	88 to 89
2.0	Above Average	85 to 87
2.25	Average	83 to 84
2.5	Fair	80 to 82
2.75	Below Average	77 to 79
3.0	Passing	75 to 76
5.0	Failure	74 and below
AW	Authorized Withdrawal	

To gather the data necessary for this study, a survey questionnaire will be used. Moreover, the following steps shall be observed:

1. The researchers sought approval from the research instructor, adviser, and College Dean to conduct the study.
2. The researchers wrote a letter to every Department Dean to conduct the study and inform them of the objectives and benefits of the study.
3. The researchers submitted a copy of the manuscript to the Ethical Review Committee (ERC). Once clearance is obtained, the study can commence.
4. The researchers reminded respondents that their grades will remain confidential and will only be used for research purposes.
5. The researchers asked the coordinator to provide their final grades in Purposive Communication from the previous semester as part of the questionnaire. The researchers will coordinate with each department's coordinator to survey a designated area. Once the location is set, the researchers will distribute the survey questionnaires. During the process, the researchers will monitor the respondents and allocate 10 minutes for them to complete the survey. The researchers will ensure that all respondents are seated comfortably and able to answer the questionnaire without any issues. After the respondents have finished, the researchers will collect the questionnaires and ensure the utmost confidentiality, with the answers remaining known only to the researchers. To ensure accuracy, respondents will be encouraged to provide their ID numbers, which the research adviser will verify.
6. After all data has been collected, the data will now be analyzed.
7. After the data analysis, the questionnaires containing respondent information would be properly disposed of as soon as the data has been fully analyzed and interpreted. The shredded materials would be placed in a designated

confidential waste disposal bin. All data would be disposed of six (6) months after the research findings have been finalized and reported, or upon their finalization and reporting.

Ethical Consideration

The researchers are committed to upholding ethical standards throughout the conduct of this study. Before data collection, a formal request letter will be submitted to the Department Deans and Program Coordinators of the College of Computer Studies and the School of Teacher Education at DMC College Foundation, Inc., seeking permission to conduct the study. Upon receiving approval, the researchers will proceed with the administration of survey questionnaires to the selected participants.

This research has been reviewed and approved by the Ethics Review Committee of DMC College Foundation, Inc., and is conducted under ERC Protocol No. **087-2024-2025**. The researchers will strictly adhere to all ethical guidelines set forth by the institution.

For the data-gathering instrument, which consists of an adopted questionnaire, the researchers will ensure that proper acknowledgment and citation are given to the original authors and relevant sources.

Confidentiality and privacy of all respondents will be prioritized at every stage of the research. Participation in the study will be voluntary, and informed consent will be obtained before participation. All data and personal information collected will be treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes. After data analysis and interpretation, the collected data will be securely stored and subsequently disposed of in accordance with ethical research practices to ensure the protection of respondent identity and privacy.

Results

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Gender, Age, and Program

Characteristic		Counts (n=46)	% of total
Gender	Male	35	76.1
	Female	11	23.9
Age	18 years old	6	13.0
	19 years old	28	60.9
	20 years old	8	17.4
	21 years old	4	8.7
Program	BSIT	38	82.6
	BSED	8	17.4

Table 3 presents the demographic characteristics of the 46 student respondents in DMCCFI, detailing their gender, age, and academic program. Understanding these demographics is crucial for contextualizing their attitudes toward English vocabulary learning.

As can be seen in Table 3, most respondents are male (76.1%), while female respondents constitute only 23.9%. This gender distribution reflects the common enrollment trends in technology-oriented programs such as the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT), which comprises 82.6% of the participants, while the remaining 17.4% are students from the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) program. In terms of age, the majority are 19 years old (60.9%), followed by 20-year-olds (17.4%), and a smaller percentage are either younger (18 years old, 13.0%) or slightly older (21 years old, 8.7%). This indicates a sample largely composed of young male students in a technical field, which may influence their learning attitudes and behaviors.

The respondent profile highlights the importance of considering demographic factors when analyzing attitudes toward English vocabulary learning, as these can significantly impact students' engagement and success.

Table 4. Students' Attitude in Learning English Language in Terms of Behavioral Indicators

	Behavioral Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Description
1	Having a good and sufficient English vocabulary boosts my confidence.	4.30	0.81	Strongly Agree
2	Studying English vocabulary helps me to have good relationships with others.	4.24	0.85	Strongly Agree
3	When I hear my classmate having good vocabulary skills, I like to practice speaking with him/her.	3.83	1.04	Agree
4	Learning English vocabulary helps me to improve my personality.	4.09	0.91	Agree
5	Learning new vocabulary is a waste of time.	1.8	1.05	Disagree
6	I put off my English homework as much as possible because I don't understand the vocabularies.	2.3	1.03	Disagree
7	I am not relaxed whenever I must speak in my English class because I have low vocabulary.	3.02	0.95	Neither Agree nor Disagree
8	I feel embarrassed to speak English in front of my classmates.	3.11	1.06	Neither Agree nor Disagree
9	When I miss the class, I never ask my friends or teachers for the homework on what has been taught.	2.24	1.18	Disagree
10	I do not feel enthusiastic to come to class when the English is being taught.	2.13	1.0	Disagree
OVERALL ASSESSMENT		3.11	0.415	Neither Agree nor Disagree

*Scoring Description: 1.00-1.80- Strongly Disagree (very negative attitude), 1.81-2.60- Disagree (negative attitude), 2.61-3.40- Neither Agree nor Disagree (neutral or uncertain attitude), 3.41-4.20- Agree (positive attitude), 4.21-5.00- Strongly Agree (very positive attitude) **SD= Standard Deviation*

Table 4 assesses students' behavioral attitudes toward learning English vocabulary, focusing on their actions and habits related to vocabulary acquisition.

As shown in the table, the overall mean score for behavioral indicators is 3.11, which falls into the "Neither Agree nor Disagree" range, indicating a neutral behavioral stance toward learning English vocabulary. This neutrality is particularly significant because it contrasts with the stronger cognitive and emotional attitudes seen in later tables. While students recognize and appreciate the value of vocabulary learning, their actual behaviors—such as class participation, homework completion, and speaking practice, do not consistently reflect strong engagement.

Illustratively, given the high mean scores for specific items, such as “Having a good and sufficient English vocabulary boosts my confidence” (4.30) and “Studying English vocabulary helps me to have good relationships with others” (4.24), show that students associate vocabulary with social and academic empowerment. These positive behaviors, however, appear to be counterbalanced by problematic tendencies. For example, the statement “I put off my English homework as much as possible because I don’t understand the vocabulary” scored low at 2.30, indicating a avoidance behavior among some students. Similarly, the statement “I do not feel enthusiastic to come to class when English is being taught” also received a low mean (2.13), further revealing the disconnection between recognition and participation.

Another noteworthy insight is the average scores around anxiety-related behaviors, such as being embarrassed to speak English (3.11) or not feeling relaxed when required to speak in class (3.02), both of which hover around the neutral mark. These findings display that despite students understanding the importance of vocabulary, a subset experiences inhibition or discomfort in real classroom scenarios, especially in oral communication tasks.

Consistently, the findings are supported by the study of Ferrer and Carmen (2022), which found that students' behavioral attitudes, such as consistent practice and proactive learning strategies, are critical for effective vocabulary acquisition, especially among Filipino students.

Collectively, based on the findings, this behavioral neutrality may stem from a range of factors, including previous learning experiences, classroom climate, teaching strategies, or even peer dynamics. It shows that traditional, teacher-centered methods of vocabulary instruction do not adequately stimulate student engagement or foster autonomy. Additionally, in a curriculum that might prioritize grammar and reading over communicative use of vocabulary, students may not be getting enough active practice, leading to passivity in behavior despite positive emotional or cognitive dispositions.

Table 5. Students’ Attitude in Learning English Language in Terms of Cognitive Indicators

	Cognitive Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Description
1	Being good at learning English vocabulary will help me study other subjects well.	4.35	0.82	Strongly Agree
2	I have more knowledge and more understanding when studying English.	3.91	0.86	Agree
3	In my opinion, people who have sufficient vocabularies are very knowledgeable.	3.96	0.99	Agree
4	Studying English language vocabulary helps me communicate in English effectively.	4.33	0.82	Strongly Agree
5	Studying English language vocabulary makes me able to create new thoughts.	4.20	0.91	Agree
6	Learning new vocabularies everyday widens my horizon.	4.02	1.04	Agree
7	Frankly, I study English just to pass the exams.	2.80	1.00	Neither Agree nor Disagree
8	I cannot apply the knowledge from English subject in my real life.	2.37	1.10	Disagree
9	I am not satisfied with my performance in the English subject.	2.83	1.06	Neither Agree nor Disagree
10	In my opinion, English language is difficult and complicated to learn.	3.13	1.24	Neither Agree nor Disagree

OVERALL ASSESSMENT	3.59	0.478	Agree
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*Scoring Description: 1.00-1.80- Strongly Disagree (very negative attitude), 1.81-2.60- Disagree (negative attitude), 2.61-3.40- Neither Agree nor Disagree (neutral or uncertain attitude), 3.41-4.20- Agree (positive attitude), 4.21-5.00- Strongly Agree (very positive attitude) **SD= Standard Deviation*

Table 5 examines the cognitive dimensions of students’ attitudes toward learning English vocabulary, focusing on perceptions, beliefs, and intellectual associations.

The overall cognitive attitude score of 3.59 indicates that students generally “Agree” with the intellectual and functional benefits of learning English vocabulary. Findings show that students perceive vocabulary learning as valuable not only for language proficiency but also for broader academic and personal development.

Items such as “Being good at learning English vocabulary will help me study other subjects well” (4.35) and “Studying English vocabulary helps me communicate in English effectively” (4.33) received some of the highest scores, interpreted as Strongly Agree. These indicate students’ belief in the instrumental role of vocabulary in academic performance and communication skills, which reflects an understanding of the cross-curricular utility of language proficiency. Further supported by the study by Ayana H. et al. (2024), which emphasized that students’ cognitive beliefs about vocabulary learning significantly influence their motivation and the strategies they employ, thereby affecting their overall language proficiency.

However, the middle-to-lower range scores for statements such as “I study English just to pass the exams” (2.80) and “I cannot apply the knowledge from the English subject in my real life” (2.37) reveal an important cognitive conflict. While students acknowledge the theoretical and practical value of vocabulary knowledge, some do not feel confident in applying it outside the classroom. This may clearly point to issues with transfer of learning, where classroom instruction fails to connect sufficiently with real-life contexts, especially in a largely technical student population.

Cognitively, these mixed results display a partial internalization of the value of vocabulary learning. Students see the benefits but are still developing the metacognitive strategies needed to make vocabulary knowledge personally meaningful and applicable.

Table 6. Students’ Attitude in Learning English Language in Terms of Emotional Indicators

	Emotional Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Description
1	I appreciate the strategy of teaching English Vocabulary.	4.3	0.81	Strongly Agree
2	Studying English language vocabulary is enjoyable.	4.09	0.98	Agree
3	I feel proud when studying English language vocabulary.	4.17	0.82	Agree
4	Studying English subject makes me feel more confident.	4.24	0.90	Strongly Agree
5	I am interested in studying English vocabulary.	4.24	0.77	Strongly Agree
6	Knowing English is an important goal in my life.	4.09	0.81	Agree
7	I look forward to the time I spend in English class.	3.85	0.99	Agree
8	Studying English makes me have a good emotion (feelings).	3.96	0.84	Agree

9	I have low vocabulary that’s why I enjoyed every time there are new vocabulary taught in the class.	3.63	1.16	Agree
10	I really have little interest in my English class.	2.78	1.26	Neither Agree nor Disagree
OVERALL ASSESSMENT		3.93	0.645	Agree

*Scoring Description: 1.00-1.80- Strongly Disagree (very negative attitude), 1.81-2.60- Disagree (negative attitude), 2.61-3.40- Neither Agree nor Disagree (neutral or uncertain attitude), 3.41-4.20- Agree (positive attitude), 4.21-5.00- Strongly Agree (very positive attitude) **SD= Standard Deviation*

Table 6 examines the emotional responses of students toward English vocabulary learning, including feelings of enjoyment, interest, and confidence.

The emotional indicators yielded an overall mean of 3.93, the highest among the three domains, which suggests that students have a predominantly positive affective response to learning English vocabulary. This is a crucial finding, as emotional engagement is often a key predictor of long-term motivation and learning persistence.

Statements such as “I appreciate the strategy of teaching English vocabulary” (4.30), “I am interested in studying English vocabulary” (4.24), and “Studying English makes me feel more confident” (4.24) show that the learning environment is emotionally supportive and the content is perceived as engaging. Students’ positive feelings toward vocabulary instruction and their sense of confidence and pride when studying suggest a high level of emotional involvement in the language learning process. Consistent with the study by Tan S.E. et.al. (2024), which found that positive emotions, such as enjoyment and curiosity, significantly enhance vocabulary knowledge, while negative emotions like anxiety can hinder learning.

However, there is still some ambivalence, as seen in the statement “I have little interest in my English class,” which had a mean of 2.78. This slight emotional dissonance may reflect variations in teaching delivery or student interest depending on specific class topics or instructional styles.

These high emotional scores, combined with moderate cognitive ones and neutral behavioral scores, point to a potential motivational bottleneck. Comprehensively based on the findings, students feel good about learning and understanding its benefits, but are not always behaviorally proactive, possibly due to a lack of reinforcement or structured opportunities for active use.

Table 7. Summary of the Students’ Attitude in Learning the English Language

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Description
Behavioral Indicators	3.11	0.415	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Cognitive Indicators	3.59	0.478	Agree
Emotional Indicators	3.93	0.645	Agree
OVERALL ASSESSMENT	3.54	0.407	Agree

*Scoring Description: 1.00-1.80- Strongly Disagree (very negative attitude), 1.81-2.60- Disagree (negative attitude), 2.61-3.40- Neither Agree nor Disagree (neutral or uncertain attitude), 3.41-4.20- Agree (positive attitude), 4.21-5.00- Strongly Agree (very positive attitude) **SD= Standard Deviation*

Table 7

summarizes the students' attitudes across behavioral, cognitive, and emotional domains. This summary table provides a comparative overview of the students' attitudes across behavioral (3.11), cognitive (3.59), and emotional (3.93) domains. The overall weighted mean of 3.54 places the general attitude toward English vocabulary learning in the “Agree” range.

The most striking aspect is the disparity between emotional and behavioral indicators. Emotional engagement is high, suggesting that students feel positive and connected to their vocabulary learning experiences. Cognitively, they understand the relevance of vocabulary in both academic and practical terms. However, their behaviors, such as active practice, seeking help, and following up on missed lessons, do not consistently reflect this enthusiasm and understanding.

In the study of Ayana, H. et al. (2024). It was found that students' attitudes toward vocabulary learning, encompassing cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects, significantly predict their vocabulary knowledge, highlighting the importance of aligning attitudes with learning behaviors.

This disconnect underscores a classic educational challenge: transforming passive or emotional approval into consistent, goal-directed action. In conclusion, based on the findings, educational strategies should aim to align students' positive feelings and beliefs with their behaviors, possibly through goal setting, self-monitoring, and reflective practices that encourage active engagement. While students hold positive cognitive and emotional attitudes toward vocabulary learning, there is a need to foster behaviors that reflect these attitudes to enhance learning outcomes.

Table 8. Academic Performance of the Respondents in the Purposive Communication Course

Characteristic		N	Mean (Percentage Grade)	Mean (Grade Point)	SD	Description
Gender	Male	35	89.6	1.66	0.359	Very Good
	Female	11	92.2	1.48	0.284	Very Good
Age	18 years old	6	90.3	1.58	0.376	Very Good
	19 years old	28	90.4	1.60	0.393	Very Good
	20 years old	8	90.5	1.59	0.229	Very Good
	21 years old	4	88.3	1.81	0.125	Good
Program	BSIT	38	90.2	1.62	0.322	Very Good
	BSED	8	90.1	1.59	0.481	Very Good
OVERALL ASSESSMENT		46	90.2	1.61	0.348	Very Good

*Scoring Description: 1.00-1.80- Strongly Disagree (very negative attitude), 1.81-2.60- Disagree (negative attitude), 2.61-3.40- Neither Agree nor Disagree (neutral or uncertain attitude), 3.41-4.20- Agree (positive attitude), 4.21-5.00- Strongly Agree (very positive attitude) **SD= Standard Deviation*

Table 8 presents the academic performance of the 46 respondents in their Purposive Communication course, analyzed by gender, age, and academic program. The overall mean score of 1.61 (90.2) falls under the "Very Good" category, indicating generally strong academic performance in the subject.

Both male (mean = 1.66) and female (mean = 1.48) respondents performed very well, with females achieving slightly higher scores. This aligns with Al-Saadi's (2020) previous study, suggesting that female students often excel in language-related subjects due to stronger verbal abilities and greater diligence in coursework. The relatively low standard deviations across gender also reflect consistency in academic outcomes, suggesting minimal disparity within each subgroup.

In terms of age, the 21-year-old group had the lowest performance (mean = 1.81 – "Good"), which may be attributed to outlier behaviors, transfer delays, or other factors affecting study continuity. Meanwhile, students aged 19, who comprise the majority, maintained strong performance (mean = 1.60). Program-wise, both BSIT (mean = 1.62) and BSED (mean = 1.59) students scored within the "Very Good" range. However, BSED students displayed slightly higher variation (SD = 0.481), perhaps reflecting greater individual differences in language competencies or interests.

The uniformly high scores indicate that students, regardless of background, are capable of excelling in English subjects when appropriately supported. It also implies that their generally positive emotional and cognitive attitudes toward vocabulary learning (as seen in Tables 5 and 6) may contribute to academic success, even if behavioral indicators remain neutral.

Table 9. Test of Difference Between the Students' Attitude Towards Learning English Language Vocabulary when the Respondents are grouped in Terms of Gender

Indicators	Statistic	p-value	Interpretation	Decision of Ho
A. Behavioral Indicators	191	0.969	Not Significant	Fail to reject
B. Cognitive Indicators	150	0.278	Not Significant	Fail to reject
C. Emotional Indicators	91.5	0.009	Significant	Reject
Overall	125	0.084	Not Significant	Fail to reject

Significance level=0.05

Table 9 examines whether gender has a statistically significant effect on students' attitudes toward learning English vocabulary. The results show no significant differences in behavioral ($p = 0.969$) and cognitive ($p = 0.278$) indicators, nor in overall attitude ($p = 0.084$), as the p values are greater than the significance level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis is retained. However, there is a significant difference in emotional indicators ($p = 0.009$), with the null hypothesis being rejected.

This finding reveals that while male and female students share similar beliefs and behaviors regarding vocabulary learning, their emotional responses differ significantly. The significant result in the emotional domain suggests that one gender, most likely female students, based on prior research, may exhibit greater emotional engagement, including enjoyment, pride, or motivation, when studying vocabulary.

These differences could stem from gender-based classroom dynamics, self-perception, or prior educational experiences. Female students, as research suggests Al-Saadi, 2020), often report higher levels of affective engagement in language subjects, which translates into better participation and performance. On the other hand, male students may be less expressive or responsive to emotional stimuli in academic settings, especially in a technical learning environment.

Understanding these emotional differences is critical for educators, as emotional engagement significantly influences motivation and long-term retention. Incorporating emotionally responsive teaching strategies, such as positive feedback, collaborative tasks, and student-centered approaches, could help reduce the gender gap in emotional engagement.

Table 10. Test of Difference Between the Students' Attitude Towards Learning English Language Vocabulary when the Respondents are grouped in Terms of Age

Indicators	Statistic	p-value	Interpretation	Decision of Ho
A. Behavioral Indicators	1.88	0.598	Not Significant	Fail to reject
B. Cognitive Indicators	3.31	0.346	Not Significant	Fail to reject
C. Emotional Indicators	4.34	0.227	Not Significant	Fail to reject
Overall	1.13	0.770	Not Significant	Fail to reject

Significance level=0.05

Table 10 tests whether students' attitudes toward English vocabulary learning differ across age groups. The results show no significant differences in behavioral ($p = 0.598$), cognitive ($p = 0.346$), emotional ($p = 0.227$), or overall attitudes ($p = 0.770$), as the p-values are greater than the significance level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that students, regardless of whether they are 18, 19, 20, or 21 years old, generally share similar attitudes toward vocabulary learning.

The absence of significant age-related differences is generally explained by the narrow age range among respondents, all of whom are within the late-adolescent to early-adulthood developmental stage. During this period, learners typically share common academic experiences and cognitive capacities, leading to homogeneous learning attitudes. Additionally, the institution's curriculum and instructional methods are likely consistent across programs, providing a uniform exposure to English-language instruction.

Nevertheless, no statistically significant differences were found; subtle age-related tendencies might still influence engagement, especially in maturity-related areas such as responsibility, time management, and metacognitive awareness. While older students (21) had slightly lower academic performance in Table 6, their attitudes may not differ because they share the same learning environment.

Conclusively, for practitioners, these results suggest that age alone should not dictate differentiated instruction in English vocabulary learning at this level. Instead, other variables, such as learning styles, prior exposure, and academic major, may be more predictive of differences in attitude.

Table 11. Test of Difference Between the Students' Attitude Towards Learning English Language Vocabulary when the Respondents are grouped in Terms of Program

Indicators	Statistic	p-value	Interpretation	Decision of Ho
A. Behavioral Indicators	144.0	0.827	Not Significant	Fail to reject
B. Cognitive Indicators	142.0	0.782	Not Significant	Fail to reject
C. Emotional Indicators	56.5	0.006	Significant	Reject
Overall	102	0.151	Not Significant	Fail to reject

Significance level=0.05

Table 11 evaluates whether students’ attitudes toward vocabulary learning differ significantly based on academic program. The data show that behavioral ($p = 0.827$), cognitive ($p = 0.782$), and overall ($p = 0.151$) indicators do not differ significantly; thus, the null hypothesis regarding the program is retained. In contrast, emotional indicators do ($p = 0.006$), prompting rejection of the null hypothesis for that domain only.

This indicates that while BSIT and BSED students may act (behaviorally) and think (cognitively) similarly about vocabulary learning, their emotional responses differ. This is particularly relevant given the contextual roles that language plays in each program. BSED students, who are being trained to become future educators, often form a stronger emotional connection to language learning because their curriculum focuses on communication, pedagogy, and literacy. BSIT students, by contrast, may view language as a support tool rather than a primary skill, which can lead to lower emotional engagement.

The emotional disparity is consistent with research by Getie (2020), which found that students in education-related fields typically express more positive emotional attitudes toward language learning due to its direct relevance to their future professions.

This result signals a need for differentiated instructional approaches. Particularly for technical students, vocabulary instruction might need to be more contextualized—integrating programming languages, technical terms, or English for Specific Purposes (ESP) strategies to foster greater emotional investment.

Table 12. Test of the Relationship Between the Students’ Attitude Towards Learning English Language Vocabulary and Their Academic Performance

Variables	Statistic	p-value	Interpretation	Decision of Ho
Students’ Attitude Towards Learning English Language Vocabulary vs Academic Performance	0.032	0.833	Not Significant	Fail to reject

Significance level=0.05

Table 12 explores whether a significant relationship exists between students’ attitudes toward English vocabulary and their academic performance. The correlation result ($r = 0.032$, $p = 0.833$) indicates a statistically insignificant relationship, as the p-value exceeds the significance level of 0.05, meaning that no direct linear association can be established in this sample. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0 : There is no significant relationship between students’ attitude towards learning English language vocabulary and academic performance) was not rejected.

This finding is intriguing, especially given that students reported generally positive cognitive and emotional attitudes and overall high academic performance (Table 6). The lack of correlation may point to the presence of mediating or confounding variables, such as study habits, prior language exposure, or instructor effectiveness, that dilute the direct impact of attitude on performance.

It is also possible that students’ grades in Purposive Communication reflect not only vocabulary knowledge but also other competencies such as essay writing, grammar, oral communication, and critical thinking. Thus, while students may feel positively about vocabulary learning, this attitude may not directly translate into higher grades unless supported by the use of strategies and skill transfer.

This outcome does not undermine the importance of fostering positive attitudes; rather, it highlights the need for a more holistic approach to performance assessment. Instructors should consider triangulating grades with qualitative assessments of vocabulary use and self-regulation strategies to understand the link between attitude and achievement better better.

Discussion

The majority of the 46 students who responded were male (76.1%), aged 19 (60.9%), and enrolled in the BSIT program (82.6%). This demographic profile represents a young, predominantly male technical student population. Regarding attitudes toward English vocabulary learning, the overall attitude score was 3.54, indicating broad agreement and a favorable orientation toward vocabulary learning. Emotional attitudes had the highest rating ($M = 3.93$), indicating students' delight, interest, and confidence. Cognitive views also scored highly ($M = 3.59$), indicating that students believe in the importance and utility of vocabulary for academic achievement and communication. However, behavioral attitudes remained neutral ($M = 3.11$), indicating limited sustained participation in vocabulary-related tasks and practices.

Academically, students performed very well in their Purposive Communication course, with an aggregate mean of 1.61 (90.2%), indicating no significant gender or program-related disadvantage. Statistically, difference tests revealed that gender and program had a significant impact on emotional attitudes ($p = 0.009$ and $p = 0.006$, respectively), implying that female and education students are more emotionally invested in language learning. However, there was no significant difference in behavioral, cognitive, or overall views between genders, ages, or programs. Finally, the study discovered no significant relationship ($r = 0.032$, $p = 0.833$); the null hypothesis was retained, as the p -value is greater than the significance level of 0.05, utilizing Spearman's correlation between students' general attitude toward English vocabulary and academic performance in the topic, showing that attitude alone may not be sufficient to predict accomplishment outcomes.

Conclusion

The present study emphasized a critical insight into students' attitudes toward English vocabulary acquisition: while emotional and cognitive responses were generally positive, these favorable attitudes did not always translate into consistent learning behaviors. Students viewed vocabulary learning as both meaningful and enjoyable, yet this enthusiasm often fell short of leading to regular, active engagement. This gap between what students felt and what they did underscored the importance of examining not only learners' perceptions but also their actual practices.

The findings revealed that students exhibited strong emotional and cognitive attitudes toward vocabulary learning, particularly among female and BSED students, who likely found greater resonance with communication-centered academic tracks. In contrast, BSIT students demonstrated comparatively lower emotional engagement, suggesting the need for vocabulary instruction that aligned more closely with technical and discipline-specific contexts. Despite these attitude patterns, a behavioral neutrality was observed across groups, and notably, no significant relationship was found between attitude and English academic performance. This indicated that success in English language learning depended on factors beyond attitude alone, such as instructional quality, learner strategies, and assessment frameworks.

The broader implications of these findings pointed toward a need for instructional design that did more than foster positive sentiment. Teachers and curriculum developers were encouraged to consider how to effectively harness emotional engagement to drive behavioral outcomes. Tailored interventions that reflected learners' academic backgrounds and preferences were deemed essential, particularly for students in more technical or less language-focused programs. Equipping learners with structured, context-relevant tools could help convert positive attitudes into regular practice.

In contributing to the field of language education, this study offered a nuanced understanding of the interplay between emotional, cognitive, and behavioral aspects of vocabulary learning attitudes. By highlighting the limitations of attitude as a standalone predictor of success, the research drew attention to the multifaceted nature of language acquisition. It reinforced the notion that a holistic approach—one that included motivation, learning strategies, and context-based instruction—was vital for fostering effective vocabulary development.

Looking ahead, future research is encouraged to focus on developing and evaluating instructional interventions that target the behavior-attitude gap. Such studies could explore the use of gamification, personalized learning, or vocabulary practice embedded in real-world applications to increase engagement. It was recommended that educators proactively design vocabulary instruction that not only sparks interest but also sustain consistent learner participation. Addressing this misalignment was seen as key to promoting long-term language competence and academic success.

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